

EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION OF THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF THE PLA-PAPER COMPOSITE

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Keywords: Biodegradable polymers, Recycled Paper, Sustainable composites

ABSTRACT

Discarded paper is mainly used for the production of recycled paper, and other applications have not been yet fully explored in detail. On the other hand, poly-lactide (PLA) is a biodegradable polyester derived from renewable resources such as cornstarch and sugarcane, among others. In the present work, the mechanical properties of a laminated composite made of paper and PLA laminae (PLAPER) were determined experimentally. The composite specimens were subjected to compression, tension, bending, hardness, and impact tests. The obtained mechanical properties of the PLAPER indicate its potential applications in many areas, with the advantage of being a biodegradable and sustainable material with lower weight and cost, and comparable mechanical behavior.

1 INTRODUCTION

The search for new and sustainable construction materials has increased during the recent years all over the world. This search is justified due to the carbon print generated during the manufacturing process of conventional materials such as steel, concrete and masonry units. Besides, most of composite materials use different types of polymers as matrix, being polymers hard to degrade due to their resistances to heat, light and chemicals. The main objective of this study is to explore the potential applications of a laminated composite made of poly-lactide (PLA) and paper by means of the evaluation of its mechanical properties.

2 MATERIALS

Poly-lactide (PLA) was discovered by Carothers at DuPont in 1932 [1]. PLA is biodegradable polyester derived from renewable resources such as cornstarch and sugarcane, among others. PLA has several advantages in front of conventional and other biopolymers including: (a) it is produced by fermentation of renewable agricultural sources; (b) fixation of important quantities of carbon dioxide in the production of the agricultural source; (c) energy savings; (d) one hundred percent recyclable by hydrolysis or alcoholysis; (e) reduction of landfill volumes; and (g) improvement of agricultural economy, among others [2]. PLA has unique properties like good appearance, high mechanical strength, and low toxicity; besides, it exhibits good barrier performance against transfer of gases, water vapor, and aroma molecules. Average mechanical properties of PLA include a tensile strength between 48 to 53 MPa, tensile modulus of elasticity of 3.5 GPa, and elongation at break varying from 30 to 240%.

On the other hand, paper is one of most used materials in everyday life. Today, 90% of paper pulp is created from wood (9-16% of pulp is made from pulp logs; the rest comes from waste wood). Paper production accounts for about 35% of felled trees. There are three categories of paper that can be used

for making recycled paper: mill broke, pre-consumer waste, and post-consumer waste. The process of waste paper recycling involves mixing used paper with water and chemicals to break it down. It is then chopped up and heated, which breaks it down further into strands of cellulose, a type of organic plant material; this resulting mixture is called pulp. It is strained through screens, which remove any glue or plastic that may still be in the mixture then cleaned, de-inked, bleached, and mixed with water. Then it can be made into new recycled paper. Recycling one ton of newsprint saves about 1 ton of wood while recycling 1 ton of printing or copier paper saves slightly more than 2 tons of wood [3]. This is because kraft pulping requires twice as much wood since it removes lignin to produce higher quality fibres than mechanical pulping processes. Trees raised specifically for pulp production account for 16% of world pulp production, old growth forests 9% and second- and third- and more generation forests account for the balance. Most pulp mill operators practice reforestation to ensure a continuing supply of trees. It has been estimated that recycling half the world's paper would avoid the harvesting of 20 million acres (81,000 km²) of forestland.[handbook]

3 PLA-PAPER MANUFACTURING PROCESS

The manufacturing process of the PLA-paper composite comprises two stages. First, the PLA laminae are obtained, and second, the PLA and paper laminae are combined to form de composite.

The production of the PLA laminae begins with the pouring of the PLA pellets into an extruding machine. The extruding machine heats the pellets and combines them producing an amorphous mass (Figure 1), which is then reduced to a thick lamina. Then, this PLA lamina is hot rolled to obtain laminae with the desired size and thickness (Figure 2). Finally, the PLA-paper composite is produced by laying up PLA and paper layers in an alternate scheme. This stack of layers if finally hot presses to guarantee the bonding between the different layers and the integrity of the composite.

Figure 1: PLA pellets extruding process.

Figure 2: PLA lamina hot-rolling process.

4 EXPERIMENTAL TESTS AND RESULTS

PLAPER specimens were subjected to tension, bending, hardness, and impact tests in order to evaluate the PLAPER mechanical behavior and its potential use in different construction applications.

A total of 8 tensile tests were performed according to the ASTM D3039 standard. The specimens were 250 mm in length, 25 mm wide, and 3 mm in thickness. The stress-strain behavior in tension is shown in figure 3.

Figure 3: Stress-strain behavior of PLAPER in tension.

It can be seen in Figure 3 the uniform behavior the different specimens exhibit indicating a low variability of the PLA tensile properties. The average values obtained from the tests are a modulus of elasticity of 6.8 GPA, a tensile strength of 74.8 MPa, and elongation at fracture of 2.6%.

PLAPER has an average tensile strength 21% higher than that of PLA. However, it exhibits strength in tension 18% lower than a similar laminated material using phenolic resin as matrix. This reduction is not important considering the biodegradability of the PLAPER composite since it uses PLA as matrix.

Eight bending tests were performed according to the ASTM D7264 standard. The specimens were 130 mm in length, 12 mm wide, and 3 mm in thickness. The load-deflection behavior in bending is shown in figure 4.

Figure 4: Load-Deflection behavior of PLAPER in bending.

Once again, the uniform behavior shown in Figure 4 indicates a low variability of the PLA bending properties. The average values obtained from the tests are a modulus of elasticity (MOE) of 4.8 GPA, and a modulus of rupture (MOR) of 99.5 MPa.

The bending strength of PLAPER (MOR) is about 270% higher than that of PLA, indicating the contribution to the tensile strength of paper laminae. Compared to the similar composite having a phenolic resin as matrix PLAPER is about 17% weaker, but once again this reduction is not important considering the biodegradability of the PLAPER composite since it uses PLA as matrix.

The shore hardness tests were performed according to the ASTM D2240 standard using a D Zwick machine on 2.69 thick specimens. The average value obtained from the 10 tests was 82.4 with a coefficient of variation of 2.3%. The impacts Izod test were performed according to the ASTM D256 standard using the corresponding Izod pendulum. The average impact resistance of ten tests was 38.3 J/m.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this work a biodegradable laminated composite made of PLA and paper laminae was prepared. The biodegradability of the components motivates the exploration of this material since it is a sustainable material. Tension, bending, hardness and impact tests were performed. Based on the results and for the material presented in this paper the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The paper laminae provide strength in tension to the PLA since the tensile and bending strengths of PLAPER are 21% and 270% higher than that of the PLA.
- Although PLAPER is not as strong as a similar material using a phenolic resin as matrix, the reduction is not important considering the sustainability of the PLAPER.
- Although not shown here, PLAPER was compared technically and economically with other construction materials. In addition to the potential contribution of the PLAPER to the sustainable construction, in terms of the mechanical properties determined in this study the potential use of this material in plastic roofs, floor tiles, and interior walls is evident.
- It is clear that more specific tests must be performed depending on the specific application of the PLAPER to be explored.

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